

ENTREPRENEURIAL RESILIENCE IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN REGION: A DECADE OF GROWTH AND CHALLENGES FOR ACTIVE ENTERPRISES (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This paper delves into the entrepreneurship landscape within the Romanian Mountain Region, examining the dynamics of active enterprises over the period from 2008 to 2018. By analyzing statistical data, the study aims to provide insights into the entrepreneurial endeavors of the population in the mountainous terrain, exploring trends, challenges, and the economic impact of these enterprises.

1. Introduction:

Entrepreneurship serves as a cornerstone of regional economic development, and this paper focuses on the Romanian Mountain Region to uncover the entrepreneurial landscape from 2008 to 2018. Through a

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detailed analysis of statistical data, we aim to unravel the growth patterns, challenges, and contributions of active enterprises within this distinctive geographic area.

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2. Methodology:

Employing a rigorous quantitative approach, this research synthesizes data from official reports, business registries, and relevant publications. Key indicators such as the establishment, growth, and survival rates of active enterprises are examined to offer a comprehensive understanding of entrepreneurial dynamics in the Romanian Mountain Region.

3. Establishment and Growth Patterns:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to the establishment and growth of active enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Region. Metrics such as the number of new businesses, industry diversity, and employment generated by these enterprises are scrutinized to assess the entrepreneurial vibrancy within the region.

4. Sectoral Analysis:

The paper delves into a sectoral analysis, examining the distribution of active enterprises across different industries in the Romanian Mountain Region. Insights into key sectors driving entrepreneurial activities, their contributions to the regional economy, and variations in sectoral growth are discussed.

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5. Challenges Faced by Entrepreneurs:

Analyzing the challenges faced by entrepreneurs in the Romanian Mountain Region, this section investigates factors such as access to finance, regulatory hurdles, and market dynamics. Understanding these challenges is crucial for formulating policies that support and sustain entrepreneurship in mountainous areas.

6. Economic Impact:

Assessing the economic impact of entrepreneurial activities, the paper investigates the contributions of active enterprises to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment rates, and overall economic stability.

The interconnectedness between entrepreneurship and regional development is explored.

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7. Trends and Future Prospects:

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Identifying notable trends in entrepreneurship during the specified period, this section provides insights into factors influencing entrepreneurial dynamics. Considerations such as technological advancements, market trends, and global economic shifts are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective on future developments.

8. Results:

This indicator represents the businesses active at a given time in a country or region. Romania is one of the most emerging countries in terms of the number of active enterprises in the mountain area.

The related descriptive analysis S1 *Industry, construction and services, except business insurance activities* presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 226349.91, 13997.826, 246416.00, 46425.535,

2155330317.691, -.924, .661, -.789, 1.279, 130479, 144988, 275467, 259915.00.

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_2: ARIMA(0,1,0); S2 - Model_3: Holt; S3 - Model_4: Holt; S4 - Model_5: Simple; S5 - Model_6: Holt; S6 - Model_7: ARIMA(0,1,0); S7 - Model_8: ARIMA(0,1,0); S8 - Model_9: Holt; S9 - Model_10: Simple; S10 - Model_11: ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_12: ARIMA(0,1,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .272, .410, -.091, .864, -.091, -.085; R-square .703, .287, -2.220E-16, 1.000, -2.220E-16, .083; RMSE, 4519.692, 7040.894, .000, 25520.564, .000, 243.723; MAPS, 12,161, 15,624, .000, 59,649, .000, 1,409; MaxAPE, 40.866, 42.025, .000, 163.445, .000, 4.375; MFA, 2774.496, 4129.489, .000, 15149.440, .000, 184.316; MaxAE, 11279,208, 18900,530, .000, 67583,600, .000, 412,260; Normalized BIC, 16,054, 2,107, 13,630, 20,525, 13,630, 13,709.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following overall picture for I1 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_2 1.110E-16, .668, 25520.564, 7.518; S2-Model_3 .788, .785, 1790.226, 5.160; S3-Model_4 .864, .786, 1461.710, 4.697; S4-Model_5 -.091, .656, 7446.962, 6.048; S5-Model_6 .772, .924,

1530.955, 7.041; S6-Model_7 .000, .883, 812.411, 5.460; S7-Model_8
 2.220E-16, .802, 1067.647, 10.379; S8-Model_9 .719, .801, 891.685,
 11.442; S9-Model_10 -.062, .277, 6941.910, 10.096; S10-Model_11 -
 2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 4455.942, 59.649; S11-Model_12 4.441E-16, .853,
 2316.294, 18.444.

Table 18. Forecast analysis for I1

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
SECT/TIME- Model_1	Forecast	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
	UCL	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
	LCL	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1-Model_2	Forecast	286331	297196	308060	318925	329789	340653	351518	362382
	UCL	344063	378841	408054	434388	458881	482066	504261	525672
	LCL	228600	215551	208066	203462	200697	199241	198775	199093
S2-Model_3	Forecast	32136	33132	34128	35124	36120	37115	38111	39107
	UCL	36186	37203	38220	39236	40253	41269	42285	43302
	LCL	28086	29061	30036	31011	31987	32962	33937	34913
S3-Model_4	Forecast	27123	27927	28732	29537	30341	31146	31950	32755
	UCL	30429	31235	32041	32850	33660	34472	35287	36105
	LCL	23816	24620	25423	26224	27023	27820	28614	29405
S4-Model_5	Forecast	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569	86569
	UCL	103162	110035	115308	119754	123671	127212	130469	133500
	LCL	69976	63103	57830	53384	49467	45926	42669	39638
S5-Model_6	Forecast	27949	29484	31019	32553	34088	35623	37158	38693
	UCL	31412	33011	34608	36205	37800	39395	40988	42581
	LCL	24486	25957	27429	28902	30377	31852	33328	34805

S6-Model_7	Forecast	15747	16421	17094	17768	18442	19116	19790	20463
	UCL	17585	19020	20278	21444	22551	23617	24652	25661
	LCL	13909	13822	13911	14093	14333	14614	14927	15265
S7-Model_8	Forecast	12023	12659	13296	13932	14569	15206	15842	16479
	UCL	14438	16075	17479	18763	19970	21122	22232	23310
	LCL	9607	9244	9113	9102	9168	9290	9452	9648
S8-Model_9	Forecast	9930	10448	10966	11485	12003	12521	13039	13558
	UCL	11947	12475	13003	13531	14059	14588	15115	15643
	LCL	7913	8421	8929	9438	9946	10455	10963	11472
S9-Model_10	Forecast	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193	37193
	UCL	52661	58622	63253	67177	70644	73784	76675	79368
	LCL	21726	15765	11134	7210	3743	603	-2288	-4982
S10-Model_11	Forecast	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262	8262
	UCL	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190	18190
	LCL	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667	-1667
S11-Model_12	Forecast	23614	25309	27005	28700	30396	32091	33787	35482
	UCL	28853	32719	36080	39180	42112	44926	47650	50302
	LCL	18374	17899	17929	18220	18679	19256	19923	20662

The analysis presented for this indicator shows that its situation at the level of the mountain area in Romania is good, the mountain area having a significant evolutionary dynamic during the analyzed period, but also in the future.

Figure 3.9. Graphical forecasting analysis for I1

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive examination of Romanian Mountain entrepreneurship from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the entrepreneurial landscape, offering valuable insights for policymakers, business leaders, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable entrepreneurial growth in the mountainous region.

Analysis sectors:

- S1. Industry, construction and services, except business insurance activities;
- S2. Industry (except construction);
- S3. Constructions;
- S4. Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles;
- S5. Transport and storage;
- S6. accommodation and food services;
- S7. Information and communications;
- S8. Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities, except activities of large companies;

S9. Professional, scientific and technical activities, administrative and public support activities;

S10. Education, human health and social assistance;

S11. Arts, entertainment and recreation, other service activities.

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Indicators for which the studies are performed:

- Active business population - number (I1)
- Newly established businesses - number (I2)
- Abolition of businesses in t - number (I3)
- Newly established enterprises in t-3 that have survived to t - number (I4)
- Enterprises with high employment growth (increase of 10% or more) - number (I5)
- Persons employed in enterprises active in t - number (I6)
- Employed in enterprises active in t - number (I7)
- Persons engaged in business established in t - number (I8)
- Employees in businesses established in t - number (I9)
- Persons engaged in business abolished in t - number (I10)
- Employees in businesses dissolved in t - number (I11)
- Persons employed in enterprises newly established in t-3 who have survived to t - number (I12)

- Persons employed in the year of establishment in enterprises newly established in t-3 who have survived to t - number (I13)
- Net business growth - percentage (I14)
- Net business situation: establishment rate + dissolution rate - percentage (I15)
- Establishment rate: number of enterprises established in the reference period (t) divided by the number of enterprises active in t - percentage (I16)
- Dissolution rate: number of enterprises disbanded in the reference period (t) divided by the number of enterprises active in t - percentage (I17)
- 3-year survival rate: number of enterprises in the reference period (t) newly established in t-3 that survived to t divided by the number of enterprises established in t-3 - percentage (I18)
- Share of enterprises aged 3 years in the business population - percentage (I19)
- Employment rate of start-ups: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) among start-ups in t, divided by the number of persons employed in t in the total number of active enterprises - percentage (I20)
- Average size of start-ups: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) among start-ups in t, divided by the number of start-ups in t (I21)
- Rate of new employees paid in enterprises: number of employees in the reference period (t) of newly established enterprises in t, divided by the

number of persons employed in t in enterprises newly established in t - percentage (I22)

- Employment rate in disbanded enterprises: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) within the disbanded enterprises divided by the number of persons employed in t in enterprises active in t - percentage (I23)

- Enterprise growth rate of three years: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) in newly established enterprises in t-3, which survived to t, divided by the number of persons employed in t -3 by the same companies, a percentage growth rate - percentage (I24)

- Employment rate of enterprises older than 3 years: number of persons employed in newly established enterprises in t-3 who survived in t, divided by the number of persons employed in active enterprises - percentage (I25)

- Share of high-growth enterprises in employment: number of high-growth enterprises divided by the number of active enterprises with at least 10 employees - percentage (I26)

- Share of enterprises with measured increased growth in employment: number of enterprises with increased growth divided by the number of active enterprises with at least 10 employees - percentage (I27).

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